

OXYFLUOBORATES AND THEIR CHEMICAL ANALOGY WITH THE SULPHATES. PART I. OXYFLUOBORATES OF ALKALI METALS, ALKALINE EARTH METALS AND LEAD

BY ASIMBIKASE RAY AND GRIHAPATI MITRA

The oxyfluoborates of lead, strontium and barium have been described. Oxyfluoborates of the alkali metals could not be prepared. The acid oxyfluoborate of potassium has, however, been prepared. Ammonium oxyfluoborate has been isolated with three molecules of BF_3 . The salts of the alkaline earth metals are sparingly soluble in water. The powder pictures of lead oxyfluoborate and barium oxyfluoborate reveal isomorphism with the corresponding sulphates.

The fluoborate ion is well established, but no mention of BF_3O^{2-} ion is found in the literature. Both from chemical as well as structural points of view, BF_3O^{2-} ion promises some interest; it has therefore been thought desirable to study the chemistry of this ion. The present paper deals with the chemistry of the oxyfluoborate of the alkali and alkaline earth metals. The structure of this new oxyfluoborate ion, in keeping with the structures of BF_4^{2-} and BeF_4^{2-} ions, should be

It is needless to mention, however, that there should be other resonating structures. The ionic and atomic radii of oxygen and fluorine are very close to each other.

Element.	Atomic radius (Å).	Ionic radius (Å).
Fluorine	0.64 (F)	1.33 (F^-).
Oxygen	0.66 (O)	1.52 (O^{2-})

Thus, it becomes apparent that BF_3O^{2-} should resemble other ions like SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , BeF_4^{2-} etc., both in size as well as in properties. Present investigation has revealed that both barium and lead oxyfluoborates are isomorphous with the corresponding sulphates. The analogy between the oxyfluoborates and the corresponding sulphates, both in composition as well as in properties, has also been recognised.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

C. P. quality compounds were taken as starting materials. The compounds were decomposed by fusing with excess of alkali metal carbonate. The amount of fluoride ions present in the compounds was determined as calcium fluoride;

boron was quantitatively estimated as methyl borate and the other elements were determined by following the usual methods (Scott, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", D. Van Nostrand Co. Inc., New York).

Oxyfluoboric Acid.— BF_3 at lower temperatures serves as the true anhydride of $\text{H}_2\text{BF}_3\text{O}$. Compounds such as $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{BF}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{BF}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were described previously. In view of the fact that aqueous solutions of $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{O} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and H_2SO_4 reveal close analogy in their equivalent conductivities (unpublished work), these compounds, so long considered as the hydrates of boron trifluoride, should better be represented as $\text{H}_2\text{BF}_3\text{O}$, $\text{H}_2\text{BF}_3\text{O} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{H}_2\text{BF}_3\text{O} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, in analogy with the corresponding hydrates of H_2SO_4 .

Oxyfluoborates of the Alkali Metals.—The pure alkali metal oxyfluoborates could not be prepared. When equimolecular quantities of HF , H_3BO_3 , and twice the molecular quantity of KF were used as the starting materials, the acid salt of the oxyfluoborate ion was obtained. The methods of preparation of the soluble oxyfluoborates have been described in detail in Part II of this series (this issue, p. 690).

The compound obtained in this case was washed and dried in the usual way and then analysed. (Found: F, 45.39; K, 31.61; B, 8.62. Calc. for KHBFB_3O : F, 45.97; K, 31.53; B, 8.73%).

The detailed description of the methods of preparation and also the results of analysis of other acid oxyfluoborates are not given here. These compounds have been reported previously in the name of the hydroxyfluoborates (Sowa *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 454; Meerwein, *Ber.*, 1933, 66, 411).

A solution of nitron acetate was added to a concentrated solution KHBFB_3O . No precipitate was obtained. KBF_4 , however, gave an instantaneous precipitation. This observation indicates that this potassium salt behaves more like KHSO_4 rather than KBF_4 .

Attempts were made to isolate the ammonium salt by heating cautiously ammonium bifluoride with the requisite quantity of boric acid. It was thought that the absence of water molecules might prevent the hydrolysis:

In this case, however, a compound having the formula $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BF}_3\text{O} \cdot 3\text{BF}_3$ was obtained. [Found: F, 70.63; NH_3 , 10.33; B, 13.09. Calc. for $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BF}_3\text{O} \cdot 3\text{BF}_3$: F, 70.51; NH_3 , 10.51; B, 13.38%].

Several compounds of this type have been described previously in the name of fluoborates and so the detailed description of the work is not given here. These compounds had, however, been represented so long (Booth and Martin, "Boron Trifluoride and its Derivatives", John Wiley and Sons, New York; "Fluorine Chemistry", edited by J. Simons, Academic Press Inc., New York, p. 203) as:

It may be suggested that oxygen is too electronegative to play the part of the central element in a complex ion, and in fact, this is the only compound reported with oxygen at the centre. After the isolation of BF_3O^{2-} ion as a separate discrete individual, these compounds should better be represented as

Further work is, however, required to confirm this.

Strontium Oxyfluoborate.—A solution of strontium nitrate was cooled to 0° by keeping the beaker in a bath of ice and salt. To this solution was added a cold saturated solution of copper oxyfluoborate with constant stirring. A white insoluble powdery substance was obtained. It was filtered under gentle suction, washed several times with water and finally with alcohol. The compound was dried at 100° and analysed. (Found: F, 32.81; B, 6.26; Sr, 50.50. SrBF_3O requires F, 33.24; B, 6.31; Sr, 51.20%).

Strontium oxyfluoborate is a finely divided crystalline solid which is sparingly soluble in water and can be heated to a high temperature without decomposition.

Barium Oxyfluoborate.—The solutions of the soluble oxyfluoborates (Part II, *loc. cit.*) have been found to be slightly acidic. A covalently bound oxygen atom is never dissociated in preference to the fluorine atom from any complex fluoride anion. The dissociation in solution may be represented as:

Due to presence of this free fluoride ion the calcium oxyfluoborate could not be isolated. Barium oxyfluoborate was isolated by suppressing the secondary dissociation by the addition of a few drops of amyl alcohol, otherwise the method of procedure was same as described under strontium oxyfluoborate. (Found: F, 25.40; B, 4.40; Ba, 61.82. BaBF_3O requires F, 25.77; B, 4.44; Ba, 62.10%).

As both barium fluoride and barium oxyfluoborate are insoluble in water, the exact nature of this white powder has been verified by X' ray analysis. The powder picture of this compound showed no line for BaF_2 . The spacings calculated from the powder picture of BaBF_3O are shown in Table I

TABLE I

<i>d.</i>	Intensity.	<i>d.</i>	Intensity.	<i>d.</i>	Intensity.
4.23	W	2.67	M	1.52	M
3.77	W	2.19	M	1.11	M
3.36	M	2.08	VS	1.33	M
3.24	M	1.65	M	1.31	W
3.01	S	1.58	W	1.28	W

VS = very strong. S = strong. M = Medium strong. W = weak.

On comparing this result with the standard spacings of BaSO₄, barium oxyfluoborate and barium sulphate are found isomorphous.

Lead oxyfluoborate was prepared by the double decomposition of the saturated solutions of lead nitrate and zinc oxyfluoborate. The heavy white precipitate formed was washed and dried by the methods described before. (Found : F, 19.34, 19.41 ; Pb, 71.01, 69.98. PbBF₃O requires F, 19.58 ; Pb, 71.20%).

This compound was precipitated in a very finely divided form. Only the more intense lines obtained from the powder picture of this compound are shown below.

TABLE II

<i>d.</i>	Intensity.	<i>d.</i>	Intensity.
4.20	S	2.04	VS
3.29	S	1.98	M
3.20	M	1.69	W
2.98	VS	1.60	W

These compounds are found to be isomorphous with sulphate on comparing their powder pictures with the standard spacings of the latter.

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